

EFFECT OF ADHESIVE DEBONDING OF CFRP AROUND WELD BEAD AND CRACK ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN STEEL PLATE

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the effect of the debonding occurred at the adhesive layer of CFRP on fatigue cracks initiated at in-plane gusset welded joints. First, the fatigue test was conducted with the specimen repaired by the externally-bonded CFRP using VaRTM technique after introducing an initial crack. The debonding area in the adhesive layer was observed by the ultrasonic phased-array system during the fatigue test. Based on fatigue test results, the stress intensity factor was calculated by FEA considering the debonding area. The results show that the crack growth rate is significantly affected by CFRP debonding.

KEYWORDS

Fatigue crack; Rrepair by externally-bonded CFRP; Debonding; Weld residual stress

INTRODUCTION

When CFRP is applied to repair fatigue crack, CFRP is bonded across the crack to reduce the crack opening displacement. However, it is known that the adhesively bonded joint at the front edge of debonding, including the crack tip, is the stress singularity, and therefore, debonding occurs near the crack tip (Colombi et al., 2003, Zheng et al., 2020). Debonding of the bonded joints reduces the bridging effect of CFRP (Matsumoto et al., 2013) and reduces the force sharing by CFRP, resulting in an increase in the crack growth rate.

In this study, the fatigue crack initiated at in-plane gusset welded joints was examined to clarify the effect of debonding of the bonded joint on the fatigue crack growth rate in fatigue crack repair by CFRP bonding. First, the effect of CFRP bonding on the crack growth life extension was examined by fatigue test based on the previous studies (Matano et al., 2022). The required carbon fiber (CF) sheets were designed to satisfy the crack growth life for the allowable crack growth length (20 mm to 40 mm). The target growth lives were established based on the fatigue strength grade of the in-plane gusset welded joints and were validated by the fatigue test. During the fatigue test, the bonded joint was vertically probed from the CFRP surface using the ultrasonic phased-array system to determine the areas of CFRP debonding. Based on the measurement results, FE models were created and numerical analysis was conducted to investigate the effect of CFRP debonding on the stress intensity factor. Some studies have used the cohesive zone modeling (CZM) to evaluate the debonding propagation (Zheng et al., 2016, Zheng et al., 2017). Due to the difference in adhesive type, the debonding propagation can vary and it is necessary to investigate and collect its data.

TEST SPECIMENS AND REPAIR METHODS

Specimen with in-plane gusset welded joints

In-plane gusset welded joints with small fatigue strength grades were targeted because fatigue cracks often initiate at the toe of the welded joint. As shown in Figure 1, the fatigue crack that initiates at the weld toe of the in-plane gusset plate was assumed, and an extension of the fatigue life by CFRP bonding repair was investigated. First, the fatigue crack grew to a certain length by fatigue test. After CFRP bonding repair was performed on specimens with a given initial crack length ($a_i = 20\text{mm}$), the fatigue test was conducted to measure the fatigue crack propagation and the CFRP debonding.

Figure 2 shows a schematic view of the specimen and CFRP bonding repair. The specimen was fabricated using a typical rolled steel for welded structures (JIS SM400A), with a base material width of 130 mm and its thickness of 10 mm. Fillets were installed at the edges of the gusset plates on one side to limit the location of fatigue crack initiation. The initial crack length a_i from one side was 20 mm. CFRP of 90 mm width was placed on both sides in the center of the specimen. Full penetration welding was performed in the area of 20 mm from the end of the in-plane gusset plate, where the fatigue crack initiates. Table 1 shows the material properties of the members used.

Figure 1: Initiation of fatigue crack at weld toe of in-plane gusset welded joints

Figure 2: Schematic view of the specimen and CFRP bonding repair

Table 1: Material properties of members used

Member	Contents	Symbols	Unit	Value
Steel plate (JIS SM400)	Young's modulus	E_s	N/mm ²	205,200
	Poisson's ratio	ν_s	—	0.29
	Yield strength	y_s	N/mm ²	301.2
Carbon fiber sheet (Intermediate modulus type, Toray UM46-40G)	Elastic modulus (0°)	E_{fT}	N/mm ²	440,000
	Elastic modulus (90°)	E_{fT}	N/mm ²	10,000
	Poisson's ratio (0°)	ν_{fL}	—	0.3
	Poisson's ratio (90°)	ν_{fT}	—	0.01
CSM (Glass)	Elastic modulus	E_c	N/mm ²	18,750
	Poisson's ratio	ν_c	—	0.3
	Shear elastic modulus	G_c	N/mm ²	7,212
Primer (Konishi E258R)	Elastic modulus	E_p	N/mm ²	3,600
	Poisson's ratio	ν_p	—	0.34
	Shear elastic modulus	G_p	N/mm ²	1,280
Impregnation resin (Toray AUP40T1)	Elastic modulus	E_m	N/mm ²	3,430
	Poisson's ratio	ν_m	—	0.39
	Shear elastic modulus	G_m	N/mm ²	1,234

CFRP bonding method and design of CFRP

The CFRP bonding method based on the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) (Kobayashi et al., 2017) was applied. Two-component epoxy resin (Toray AUP40T1) was used as an impregnation resin, and chopped strand mats (CSM) of glass fiber were used as a reinforcement material for bonding.

The required number of CF sheets was designed so that the number of cycles N_p (fatigue crack growth life) from the initial crack length a_i to the required crack length a_p is equal to or greater than the number of cycles N_f for the fatigue strength grade of the in-plane gusset welded joint.

The required crack length a_p was set to 40 mm due to the continuity of previous studies (Matano et al., 2022). Figure 3 shows the fatigue strength curves for in-plane gusset welded joints. The fatigue strength grade of in-plane gusset welded joints is G grade of the American Bureau of Shipping (ABS) and H

grade of the Japanese Society of Steel Construction (JSSC). In this study, the fatigue strength grade curve of ABS was adopted for the number of cycles N_f of the fatigue strength grade curve.

Figure 3: Fatigue strength curves of ABS (G grade) and JSSC (H grade)

The number of CF sheet layers was designed according to the following procedure. The nominal stress range of the base material was 82.8 N/mm^2 and 54.9 N/mm^2 , respectively. Assuming that no debonding occurs in the adhesive layer even if a crack propagates after CFRP repair, the fatigue crack growth life N_p for each stress range was calculated using the stress intensity factor obtained from the proposed formula (Matsumoto et al., 2013). The number of cycles N_{p20-40} that a fatigue crack propagates from $a_i = 20 \text{ mm}$ to $a_p = 40 \text{ mm}$ is calculated from the following equation based on the stress intensity factor range and the Paris's law.

$$N_{p20-40} = \int_{a_i}^{a_p} \frac{1}{C \Delta K_I^m} \Delta a \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Where ΔK_I is the stress intensity factor range considering the effect of bridging stress and in-plane gusset plate, a is the crack length, C and m are the material constants, respectively. The material constants C and m were identified as $C = 2.0 \times 10^{-11}$ and $m = 3.06$ based on the fatigue test results of the unrepaired specimens. The number of CF sheet layers was calculated to satisfy $N_p > N_f$. As a result, the required number was 4.

The development (fixed) length of CFRP was calculated based on the (JSCE 2018), and the value was 54 mm. The length of the repair section was 36 mm, and the CFRP half-length from the center of the specimen was 90 mm. The steps were installed at the end of the CFRP to prevent CFRP debonding. The step length was determined by evaluating the maximum principal stress of the adhesive using FEA. The step length was calculated by referring to the fatigue limit of the maximum principal stress (12 N/mm^2) (Thay et al., 2018) of the bonded joint. As a result, the step length was 10 mm.

Figures 4 and 5 show a schematic view of CFRP steps and the CFRP bonding situation, respectively.

Figure 4: Schematic view of CFRP steps

Figure 5: CFRP bonding situation

Fatigue test method

An electro-hydraulic servo fatigue testing machine (Shimadzu Servo Pulsar, dynamic capacity; 200 kN) was used. First, a notch (blade width: 0.4 mm × length: 2 mm) was introduced into the specimen by a thread saw, and then an initial crack was introduced by fatigue test to propagate to 20 mm. Table 2 shows the fatigue test conditions. The stress ratio R was set to 0.1. The beach mark method was applied to evaluate the crack growth rate by observing the beach marks on the crack surface after the fracture.

Table 2: Fatigue test conditions

Name of Specimen	Stress range (N/mm ²)	Targeted crack propagation life: N_{p20-40}
R4-83-C1	82.8	167,000
R4-83-C2	82.8	167,000
R4-55-C1	54.9	1,050,000
R4-55-C2	54.9	1,050,000

OBSERVATION AND MODELING OF DEBONDING OF BONDED JOINTS

Observation by ultrasonic testing

To model the debonding of bonded joints, the ultrasonic testing method was applied to observe the area of debonding during the fatigue test. To observe the area of debonding, a vertical linear scan was performed using the ultrasonic phased-array system (UPA; ZETEC TOPAZ32) and encoder.

Figure 6 shows the results observed by UPA for each number of cycles. The images show the strength of the ultrasonic waves reflected from the steel (bottom surface) as a result of digital processing. Yellow areas indicate that ultrasonic waves were strongly detected. White areas indicate areas where ultrasonic waves were not detected, and were judged to be areas where debonding (not the damage area) occurred in the adhesive layer. The crack length in the figure is the length detected by the beach mark method and is indicated by a solid red line. Since the crack tip in the UPA image is almost the same as the crack length, the white areas were estimated to be the debonding area. The results show that the debonding area increases as the number of cycles increases. The debonding area was also observed to extend in a triangular shape from the crack tip.

Figure 6: The results observed by UPA for each number of cycles

Modeling of debonding area

To model debonding by FEA, the debonding area was simplified. The UPA image shows that the debonding area extends in a triangular shape with the crack tip at the top. Assuming that the front of the debonding or the boundary of the debonding is a straight line, the relationship between the crack length and the debonding area was determined.

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the length y from the CFRP end to the crack tip ($y = a - a_i$, mm, a : crack length, a_i : initial crack length, 20 mm) and the debonding length d at the center of the crack

length. In the stress range of 82.8 N/mm^2 , the relationship between y and d is almost linear. On the other hand, in the stress range of 54.9 N/mm^2 , the relationship is generally linear, although there is some variation among the specimens. The reason for the large variation in the stress range of 54.9 N/mm^2 can be attributed to the non-uniformity within the adhesive layer under small loading.

Figure 7: Relationship between the length from the CFRP end to the crack tip and the debonding length at the center of the crack length

EVALUATION OF STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR CONSIDERING DEBONDING OF ADHESIVE LAYER AND EFFECT OF DEBONDING ON CRACK GROWTH RATE

Modeling of test specimen and debonding

FE models with solid (hexahedral) elements were created. Figure 8 shows the FE model and element mesh diagrams. The general-purpose finite element analysis software (Marc/Mentat 2019) was applied. In the boundary condition, the displacements in three directions were fixed at the end of the specimen, and the nominal tensile stress was applied in the longitudinal direction. The stress intensity factor at the crack tip was calculated based on the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT). The element dimensions of the crack tip were $0.03 \text{ mm} \times 0.03 \text{ mm}$.

Figure 8: FE model and element mesh diagrams

To model the debonding of the adhesive layer, an epoxy resin adhesive (Konishi E258R, 0.2 mm thickness) was used as a primer, and a composite adhesive layer (0.343 mm thickness) of impregnated resin (Toray AUP40T1) and CSM, respectively, were modeled. Debonding was modeled by deactivating elements to remove the adhesive layer elements in the debonding area. The debonding area was approximated as an isosceles triangle based on the experimental results.

Figure 9 shows the definition of the debonding area. When the length y from the CFRP end to the crack tip is divided into N equal parts, the debonding length d_i at the i -th y_i is expressed by Eq.2.

$$d_i = (0.0023\Delta\sigma_{sn} - 0.898)y_i \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

Since there are only two cases of stress range $\Delta\sigma_{sn}$ in this study, a linear equation was used with the stress range as a parameter. Figure 8 shows also an example of removing an adhesive layer element in the debonding area (stress range: 54.9 N/mm²) at a crack length of $a_p = 52$ mm and a debonding length of $d_i = 9.46$ mm at the edge of CFRP.

Figure 9: Definition of the debonding area

Effect of Debonding on Stress Intensity Factor

For FEA, stress intensity factors (SIFs) were calculated for crack lengths from 27 mm to 52 mm. The SIFs for crack lengths from 20 mm to 80 mm were evaluated by curve fitting based on Eq.3 using the coefficients p and q .

$$\Delta K_I = p \cdot a_p^q \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

Where a_p is the crack length. Table 3 shows the coefficients of Eq.3. The experimental values of SIFs were calculated based on Eq.1 using the material constants C , m , and the crack growth rate $\Delta a/\Delta N$ evaluated with the beach mark spacing and the number of cycles. The analytical values of SIFs were the average values of SIFs (mode I) distributed in the thickness direction of the crack tip. FEA also was performed with and without consideration of debonding.

Table 3: The coefficients of Eq.3

Stress range $\Delta\sigma_{sn}$ (N/mm ²)	with/without considering debonding	p	q
82.8	with	13.8	0.138
82.8	without	124.7	-0.547
54.9	with	25.8	-0.191
54.9	without	79.3	-0.536

Figure 10 shows the comparison of experimental and analytical values of SIFs for each stress range. The experimental values of SIFs show that the two specimens have similar behavior, although there is some variation between the two specimens. For all stress ranges, the analytical values of SIFs tended to be smaller than the experimental values for longer cracks when debonding was not considered.

In the stress range of 82.8 N/mm², the experimental values of SIFs increased with increasing crack lengths and differed from the analytical values when debonding was not considered. On the other hand, when debonding is considered, the results show that debonding has a significant effect on SIFs, and analytical values were in general good agreement with experimental values.

In the stress range of 54.9 N/mm^2 , the experimental values of SIF decreased with increasing crack length. The analytical values decreased with and without consideration of debonding, however, the values with consideration of debonding were in better agreement with the experimental values.

Figure 10: Comparison of experimental and analytical values of SIFs for each stress range

Comparison of crack growth rate

Figure 11 shows the relationship between the crack length a_p and the number of cycles N_p , which were calculated by substituting the SIFs by FEA into Eq.1 and comparing them to the experimental values, respectively.

In the stress range of 82.8 N/mm^2 , the analytical values differed from the experimental values because the crack growth rate decreased as the crack propagated when the debonding was not considered. On the other hand, when debonding was considered, the analytical values were in good agreement with the experimental values.

In the stress range of 54.9 N/mm^2 , the analytical values considering debonding were close to the experimental values. However, the two experimental values have a large scatter, and the analytical values were intermediate between the two experimental values. The experimental values show a significant decrease in crack growth rate with increasing crack length. The analytical values showed a weaker tendency. This is because the small debonding area prevented the release of weld residual stress on the compressive side, which was supposed to reduce the crack propagation rate in the experiment.

Figure 11: Relationship between crack length a_p and number of cycles N_p

SUMMARY

Fatigue cracks in in-plane gusset welded joints were repaired with CFRP, and FE models were created based on the measurement of the CFRP debonding. The findings are summarized as follows.

- (1) During the fatigue test, the vertical ultrasonic phased-array system from the CFRP surface confirmed that the debonding area extended in a triangular shape from the crack tip.
- (2) The results of the debonding measurements showed that the relationship between the crack length and its central debonding length is roughly linear.
- (3) The results of FEA considering the relationship between debonding length and crack length showed that the analytical values of stress intensity factors are similar to the experimental values and that debonding of the adhesive layer has a significant effect on crack propagation.
- (4) The results of the crack propagation analysis based on the stress intensity factor calculated by FEA considering the debonding showed good agreement with the experimental results. However, in the stress range of 54.9 N/mm^2 , the analytical results showed a smaller decrease in crack growth rate than the experimental results at longer crack lengths.

REFERENCES

- Colombi, P., Bassetti, A., Nussbaumer, A. (2003). "Crack growth induced delamination on steel members reinforced by prestressed composite patch." *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, 26(5), 429-438. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1460-2695.2003.00642.x>
- Matsumoto, R., Ishikawa, T., Hattori, A., Kawano, H. (2013). "Stress intensity factor of a cracked steel plate repaired with patch plates." *Journal of Structural Engineering, JSCE*, 59A, 798-807. [in Japanese] <https://doi.org/10.11532/structcivil.59A.798>
- Kobayashi, K., Kondo, R., Nakamura, H., Matsumoto, Y., Matsui, T., Ochi, Y. (2017). "Repair of section loss in girder end by CFRP using vacuum assisted resin transfer molding technology.", *Journal of Japan Society of Civil Engineers, Ser. A1 (Structural Engineering & Earthquake Engineering (SE/EE))*, 73(5), II_20-II_31. [in Japanese] https://doi.org/10.2208/jscejsee.73.II_20
- Thay, V., Nakamura, H., Lin, F., Horii, H. (2018). "Evaluation of fatigue strength of adhesively bonded joints between steel plates and patch plates using epoxy resin adhesive.", *Journal of Japan Society of Civil Engineers, Ser. A1 (Structural Engineering & Earthquake Engineering (SE/EE))*, 74(5), II_56-II_66. [in Japanese] https://doi.org/10.2208/jscejsee.74.II_56
- The Committee on Hybrid Structures, JSCE. (2018). "Guidelines for repair and strengthening of structures using externally bonded FRP", JSCE. [in Japanese]
- Zheng, Y., Wang, Y., Hu, L., Feng, P. (2020). "Crack propagation and debonding development of CFRP laminate strengthened high-strength steel plates under fatigue loadings.", *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 768(3), [032047], <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/768/3/032047>
- Matano, A., Nakamura, H., Thay, V., Tsubokawa, T., Matsui T. (2022). "Repair effect of externally bonded CFRP on propagation life of fatigue cracks initiated at in-plane welded gusset joints." *Symposium Prague 2022*, IABSE. <https://doi.org/10.2749/prague.2022.1188>
- Zheng, B., Dawood, M. (2016). "Debonding of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer patches from cracked steel elements under fatigue loading.", *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 20(6), [04016038], [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0000694](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000694)
- Zheng, B., Dawood, M. (2017). "Fatigue crack growth analysis of steel elements reinforced with shape memory alloy (SMA)/fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composite patches.", *Composite Structures* 164, 158-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.12.077>

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.